

D6.2: Report on definition of method, objective and scope of LCA

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Glossary

BOD	Biological oxygen demand
BSF	Black soldier fly
COD	Chemical oxygen demand
Dk/Da	Do not know/ Do not answer
E-LCA	Environmental Life Cycle Assessment
F&F	Food and feed
FU	Functional unit
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCI	Life Cycle Inventory
LCIA	Life cycle impact assessment
LHV	Low heating value
MAPAMA	Ministry of agriculture and fisheries, food and environment (Spain)
OFMSW	Organic fraction of municipal solid waste
PC	Protein content
PSILCA	Product Social Impact Life Cycle Assessment
SCP	Single Cell Protein
SETAC	Society of Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry
S _i	Score of a question/subcategory
S-L	Solid-liquid
S-LCA	Social Life Cycle Assessment
SPI	Social Progress Index
UNEP	United Nations Environment Programme
VC	Value chain
VOC	Volatile organic compound
WWTP	Wastewater treatment plant

Executive summary

The sustainable development is comprised of three dimensions: economic, environmental and social. The three dimensions greatly contribute to human well-being. Therefore, the improvement of social and environmental condition is one of the main objectives of sustainability. Under this premise, the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) tool was developed and is currently the most widely used when it comes to access information about potential and real impacts of products, process and organizations. The tool can be applied to the assessment of economic, environmental and social aspects. In this way, the main objective of the present deliverable is to show how the LCA tool is used to assess the *VALUEWASTE* solution from an environmental and social point of view.

This deliverable is split into two main sections: the social LCA (S-LCA) and the environmental LCA (E-LCA). Both follow the ISO 14040 framework; however, they differ on other aspects. Moreover, the E-LCA is focused on the processes within *VALUEWASTE* solution, whereas the S-LCA considers the consortium as an entity, evaluating the impacts on stakeholders linked to the whole project.

Social Life Cycle Assessment

The S-LCA pretends to evaluate the social impacts (both positive and negative) within a process, organization, etc. focusing on different stakeholders, such as workers, local community and consumers. The S-LCA makes use of generic and site-specific data which can be quantitative, semi-quantitative or qualitative.

In this Section, the goal, scope, and methodology to perform the S-LCA of the *VALUEWASTE* solution are shown. It is important to mention that the S-LCA will be focused on those stakeholders related to the project partners. The S-LCA section is comprised of a brief introduction to the S-LCA phases, including the stages to carry it out. These phases are: i) the definition of the goal and scope of the S-LCA for the present study; ii) the life cycle inventory, where stakeholders, subcategories and social impact currently considered are shown; iii) the impact assessment, where the methodology to evaluate each social indicator is displayed; and iv) the interpretation of the results, where the subsequent steps to follow after ending the study are mentioned.

Environmental Life Cycle Assessment

The E-LCA is a time-tested assessment technique that evaluates environmental performance throughout the life cycle of a product or a service. The extraction and consumption of resources (including energy), as well as releases to air, water, and soil, are quantified throughout all stages. Their potential contribution to environmental impact categories is then assessed. These categories

include climate change, human and eco-toxicity, ionizing radiation, and resource base deterioration (e.g., water, non-renewable primary energy resources, land, etc.).

This section is comprised of i) an introduction, ii) the objective pursued by this deliverable, in its E-LCA section, iii) a general description of the LCA methodology, iv) an overall description of the production systems considered, both those that conform the baseline and those that conform the *VALUEWASTE* solution, v) the E-LCA development approaches which have been considered, and vi) the upcoming tasks which are forecasted to be developed.

1. Introduction

The *VALUEWASTE Project* is being developed at two different locations: one in Northern Europe (Kalundborg, Denmark) and the other one in Southern Europe (Murcia, Spain). This project seeks to transform the organic fraction of municipal solid waste (OFMSW) into value-added products through three value chains. In this way, the project not only obtains high value products, but also prevents the waste to be sent to landfill. The added-value products obtained from the three value chains are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 –Value-added products obtained in *VALUEWASTE Project*

A sustainability assessment requires the quantification of the impacts related to the environment, society and economy to be considered. The *VALUEWASTE Project* is committed to sustainability and, thus, these impacts have to be evaluated.

The S-LCA integrates traditional life cycle assessment by having social aspects as the main focus, whereas the E-LCA considers all the inputs and outputs of the system to evaluate its impact on diverse environmental categories, such as climate change and eutrophication.

2. Objective

The main goal of the present document is to define the method, objective and scope of the LCA methodology. This task will be performed from two points of view: environmental and social. The E-LCA will evaluate the potential environmental improvement comparing a considered baseline system to the proposed one in *VALUEWASTE Project*. The S-LCA will be carried out to assess and identify the hotspots (social impacts) on the considered stakeholders involved in *VALUEWASTE*. Both LCAs could be used to make decisions and improve both the environmental and social impacts of the projects and the citizens' perception on urban biowaste as a local source of valuable materials.

SOCIAL LIFE CYCLE ASSESSMENT

3. Social Life Cycle Assessment

3.1. Introduction

The human being footprint on the environment has been attracting society attention during the last decades. For that reason, sustainability is now an essential principle in order to protect the environment, manage its resources and decrease the release of pollutants to the atmosphere, water bodies and soils caused by human activity.

As previously said, the LCA can be performed from a social point of view, which covers the social aspects along the value chain of products or processes of an organization. The S-LCA intends to quantify the social impacts on the complete life cycle (Mattioda et al., 2019). This is a relatively recent research field where there are only 188 publications between 2003 and 2018, 35% of them published in 2018 (Huertas-Valdivia et al., 2020). Hence, there is no general consensus on the data collection process, how to select social indicators, or the characterization model to aggregate the inventory indicators into social impacts (Azimi et al., 2020). In order to address this, an important milestone in the S-LCA literature was the publication of the United Nations Environment Programme and the Society of Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry (UNEP/SETAC, respectively) guidelines which constitute a basic framework for evaluating social impacts throughout the life cycles of products (UNEP-SETAC, 2009, 2013).

In the present deliverable, it is the objective to establish the basis to develop the S-LCA for *VALUEWASTE* solution within Work Package 6 (WP6), task 6.2 (T6.2). It is important to consider that the approaches of the present report are provisional. That is to say that although some stakeholders, subcategories and social indicators have been selected, they may change during the course of the project.

As the E-LCA, the S-LCA is based on the LCA methodology defined by the International Standard Organisation, ISO (ISO, 2016). It comprises the same four phases: i) goal and scope definition, ii) the life cycle inventory analysis (LCI), iii) the life cycle impact assessment, and iv) the life cycle interpretation. These four phases are described in the following Sections. Figure 2 displays the different steps to perform the S-LCA once the objective and scope have been defined:

Figure 2 – Steps to carry out the S-LCA in VALUEWASTE Project

Selection of the stakeholders (Stage 1) → The stakeholders will be identified and definitely selected by a committee in CETENMA, leader of the task. As previously said, the UNEP/SETAC methodology proposed 5 stakeholders, but these can be modified depending on the studied system.

Selection of the subcategories (Stage 1) → Each stakeholder is composed of different subcategories. These will be agreed and definitely selected by the same CETENMA committee during the stage 1.

Selection of social indicators and questions (Stage 1 and 2) → Each subcategory is defined by social indicators, which will be evaluated by means of questions. These questions will be selected during the first stage of the S-LCA process. Once questions and social indicators are chosen, the surveys will be submitted to the different partners (stage 2), which will be in charge to spread the questionnaires among their stakeholders.

Collection and evaluation of answers (Stage 2) → The collection of answers will be carried out by the different partners of VALUEWASTE Project; whereas the evaluation of answers will be performed in CETENMA using the methodology described in *Impact Assessment* (Section 3.2.3).

Interpretation of results (Stage 3) → The interpretation of the results will be done at the end of the study to reach conclusions, provide recommendations and identify those social aspects to be improved within the different stakeholders.

3.2. Phases of the S-LCA

Throughout this Section, the four phases within the S-LCA methodology are discussed.

3.2.1. Goal and scope definition

The goal of the S-LCA is to assess and identify the hotspots (social impacts) of those stakeholders involved in the *VALUEWASTE Project*. Hence, the partners that comprise the project will also be evaluated in the present study, considering the Consortium as an entity. This could be used to make decisions and improve the social impacts related to each stakeholder by the different partners.

The functional unit can be considered as a crucial part of the LCA. In the case of E-LCA, selecting a functional unit can be clear. Nevertheless, this task is not straightforward for S-LCA (Martínez-Blanco et al., 2014). This is due to the fact that S-LCA evaluates social aspects, whose data and indicators are mainly qualitative (Arzoumanidis et al., 2020). In this way, an S-LCA can also be performed without using a functional unit like the study reported by Azimi et al. (2020). This was confirmed by Arzoumanidis et al. (2020), who reviewed this issue and found that about 25% of the studies did not identify a functional unit. In the present report, the functional unit is not defined, since it is difficult to refer most of the considered indicators (such as the satisfaction feeling of customers in relation to being listened to complaints by the local bodies) to this unit.

It is interesting to mention that many researchers focused the S-LCA on the different unit processes, following a similar methodology to E-LCA (Azimi et al., 2020). However, as indicated by Dreyer et al. (2006), a S-LCA has little sense if this is focused on processes, since most of the impacts are independent of these processes and they have influence on people. For this reason, a different methodology was proposed focusing the S-LCA on companies, organizations and actors within the studied system, i.e., on stakeholders.

In this way, the UNEP and SETAC performed a guideline focused on 5 stakeholders (consumers, local community, society, value chain actors and workers), including a list of 31 impact subcategories (UNEP-SETAC, 2009). Nevertheless, it is important to note that it is not necessary to take into account all the stakeholders or the 31 subcategories since it is possible to include/delete other stakeholders or subcategories.

3.2.2. Life Cycle Inventory (LCI)

The objective of the inventory analysis is to collect and analyse relevant information (inventory indicators). Therefore, the first step is to identify the source of these data. The best option would be to collect all data related to the social dimension visiting all the places and stakeholders linked to the

product(s) life cycle. However, this procedure is to be avoided because it would be costly and lengthy. Therefore, it is recommended to collect data from other sources like literature review, internet sites, sustainability reports and surveys. However, it must be underlined that most of the information will come from surveys. Databases such as PSILCA (Maister et al., 2020) and indexes like the SPI (The Social Progress Imperative, 2020) might also be considered.

In this way, the surveys will be composed of questions directed to the different stakeholders, which will be chosen during stage 1 (Figure 2). The questionnaire will consist of five-scale Likert type questions, yes/no questions and, most probably, open-ended questions. The Likert scale questions are employed to assess subjective data like worker's comfort level.

The inventory indicators currently considered for the S-LCA of *VALUEWASTE Project* are listed as a function of the different stakeholders and subcategories. These indicators are shown in Table 1, classified by stakeholder and subcategory. It is important to mention that the indicators, subcategories, and stakeholder may change during the development of the S-LCA.

Table 1 – Social indicators as a function of the stakeholder and the subcategory considered

Stakeholder	Subcategory	Social Indicator (Inventory Indicator)
Workers	Fair salary	Workers' wage compared to the minimum wage
	Freedom of association and collective bargaining	Risk of not having the right to strike
		Risk of not having freedom of association and collective bargaining
	Working hours	Average working hours per week
		Extra working hours: compensation in terms of extra salary or free time
		Number of holidays
		Work-life balance situation
	Forced labour	Risk of forced labour
	Equal opportunities / Discrimination	Gender/race opportunities
		Gender/race opportunities vs individual skills
		Equality of basic salary by employee category
	Health and safety	Emissions, biological agents, level of noise exposure
		Protection and prevention measures
		Occurrence of occupational accidents
		Workers' comfort level
Presence of a formal policy concerning health and safety		
Society	Public commitments to sustainability issues	Existence of public sustainability report
		Engagement of the entity regarding sustainability
	Contribution to economic development	Job Creation
		Kind of job created
	Corruption	Controls to prevent corruption
	Technology development	Involvement in technology transfer program or projects
		Partnerships in research and development
Investment in technology		

Table 1 – Social indicators as a function of the stakeholder and the subcategory considered (Continued)

Stakeholder	Subcategory	Social indicator (Inventory indicator)
Local community	Safe and healthy living conditions	Emissions, biological agents, level of noise, odours exposure
		Protection and prevention measures
	Local employment	Promotion of local employment in the production area
		Training courses for the employees
		Percentage of employees with higher/basic education
		Percentage spending on locally based suppliers
	Community engagement	Rate of willingness to have the sector close to home
		Participation of neighbours in decisions
	Citizens' participation	Existence of educational campaigns for citizens engagement
		Amount of organic waste collected
Percentage of improper material in the organic waste		
Consumers	Health and safety	Product application/consumption dangers
		Existence of health and safety measures for application/consumption
	Feedback mechanisms	Acceptance of consumers
		Capacity and quality level of the entity to manage comments/doubts/complaints
	Privacy	Existence of mechanisms to respect and protect consumers' privacy
	Transparency	Existence of mechanisms to clearly inform about products
Number of organizations which published a sustainability report		
End-of-life responsibility	Clear information provided to consumers on end-of-life options	
Suppliers	Social responsibility	Percentage of suppliers that the entity has audited with regard to environmental/social responsibility in the last 5 years
		Support to suppliers in terms of consciousness-raising and counselling concerning the social responsibility issues
	Supplier relationship	Payments on time to suppliers
		Change of supplier
		Sufficient lead time

3.2.3. Impact Assessment

The purpose of this step of the S-LCA is to provide additional information in order to assess the results obtained from the Inventory Analysis (Foolmaun & Ramjeeawon, 2013). This assessment is performed converting the indicator answers into inventory score by means of a characterization method (Azimi et al., 2020). In literature, the characterization method has been performed in different ways since there is not a unified method. For example, a binary scale (positive or negative impact) has been reported by Arcese et al. (2013) and Umair et al. (2013); a ternary scale like the manuscripts reported by Blom and Solmar (2009), where -1 denoted a positive social impact, 0 the absence of social effect, and +1 the negative social effect; and Wan (2012), where the score was at the contrary. Other authors proposed other scales. For instance, Hsu et al. (2013) used nine intervals (1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 2.5, 3.0, 3.5, 4.0, 4.5 and 5.0) to score the quantitative social aspects, whereas, for qualitative ones, the authors used a ternary scale (0.0, 0.5 and 1.0). Cirotth and Franze (2011) based the assessment on a colour scale with six associated scores: dark green (very good performance, 1), light green (good performance, 2), light blue (satisfactory performance, 3), yellow (inadequate performance, 4), orange (poor performance, 5) and red (very poor performance, 6). The authors identified as social hotspots those impacts with poor and very poor performance (orange and red colour). Other authors proposed a scoring system based on percentages. That is to say, the score of the indicator depends on a percentage range. For instance, the workers' comfort in their working place: very satisfied, satisfied, neutral, unsatisfied, and very unsatisfied. Taking into account the percentage range, this subcategory receives a score: 0-20%, 21-40%, 41-60%, 61-80% and 81-100%. This kind of scoring was used by authors like Foolmaun & Ramjeeawon (2013).

In the present study, the characterization will be based on the methodology developed by Azimi et al. (2020). The Task responsible contacted these authors in order to get a better understanding of their methodology. In principle, the questions of the survey considered in this study will be answered in different ways: i) yes/no, ii) giving a score (Likert scale), and iii) as open-ended questions (e.g., number of rests that you take during your working time). All answers will be characterized using the percentage methodology to obtain a score.

It is challenging to, at this stage, quantify the participation. Saying so, we will do our best to obtain a good and representative sample size (at least 200 people) reaching both workers and citizens involved in the different stakeholders. As mentioned, the S-LCA is focused on the *VALUEWASTE Project* partners and stakeholders. In the case of the stakeholder “workers”, the

questionnaires will be limited to those departments involved in the project for those entities with a huge number of workers (e.g., city councils).

3.2.4. Interpretation of results

According to the UNEP/SETAC methodology, this phase has several objectives: i) analyse the results, ii) reach conclusions, iii) explain the limitations of the study, and iv) provide recommendations and a report. ISO 14044 (2006) defines three main steps:

- 1) Identification of the significant issues
 - For instance, if a social impact has a poor or very poor performance when this was not considered in that way at the beginning of the study.
- 2) Evaluation of the study, including considerations of completeness and consistency
 - Some key requirements regarding the evaluation process include the performance of a critical review, the documentation of the evaluation process, the actions taken to ensure transparency, and the verifiability of results.
- 3) Conclusions, recommendations and reporting
 - Conclusions have to be drawn and a recommendation made, based on the goal and scope of the study. Recommendations are a means to formulate options for actions. The reporting should be fully transparent, implying that all assumptions, rationales, and choices are identified.

Additionally, a fourth step might be considered: Level of engagement with stakeholders. This is because it is interesting to report the participation and involvement of stakeholders in the study. This step will be included whether the stakeholders' participation is not enough, which will be defined during the study performance. This is one of the differences between E-LCA and S-LCA since E-LCA does not have this level.

*ENVIRONMENTAL
LIFE CYCLE
ASSESSMENT*

4. Environmental Life Cycle Assessment

4.1. Introduction

The objective of this Section is to present the methodology that will be followed to determine the environmental impact associated with the production of the three high-value biobased products from biowaste and the current state-of-the-art (baseline) production processes that do not start from biowaste as raw material. By comparing the environmental impact of the new biobased products with that of the baseline, it will be possible to quantify the environmental improvement of the new production model.

This task is integrated within the frame of the *VALUEWASTE Project*. *VALUEWASTE* proposes an integrated approach in urban biowaste valorising for the production of high-value biobased products, developing the first complete solution to fully valorise biowaste that can be replicated across Europe. Thus, the project intends to implement three new value chains (VC) that will use urban biowaste as raw material for its valorisation into high-value end products in a cascading process, generating economic, social and environmental benefits. These three new value chains are the following:

- i. VC 1 – Food & Feed ingredients (proteins, peptides, fats, and nucleic acids) from methanotrophic bacteria using biomethane arising from the anaerobic digestion of the biowaste.
- ii. VC 2 – Food & Feed grade protein from insect (black soldier fly) larvae fed with biowaste and/or digestate (from anaerobic digestion of urban biowaste).
- iii. VC 3 – Biobased fertilizer (struvite/ammonium sulphate blend) containing nutrients recovered from the residual dewatering liquid (from anaerobic digestion).

The development of new products or processes, in addition to being technically feasible, must be subject to evaluation from the environmental, economic and social points of view. Regarding the environmental assessment, it must be quantified the environmental impact of the developing and application/use of that new product or process, and that impact must be compared with that of the existing alternatives. That will help to decision making for developers or promoters of the new product or process, authorities, and other stakeholders.

Therefore, it is required to use a proper tool to analyse the environmental benefits and damages of these end products. To perform this analysis a standardized and sophisticated tool is used: The Environmental Life Cycle Assessment. The E-LCA compiles and evaluates the inputs, outputs,

and the potential environmental impacts of a product, process or service system throughout its life cycle.

4.2. Objective

The objective of Section 4 is to expose the E-LCA methodology which is intended to apply within the work package 6 (WP6), *Future large-scale projects*. During the WP6, the environmental performance of the technical solution developed by the *VALUEWASTE Project*, as compared with the baseline' production processes, will be evaluated. This task will be performed calculating the E-LCA for the baseline's end products and for the biobased ones obtained with the proposed solution, and then, comparing both processes.

4.3. LCA Methodology

The European Union defines the Life Cycle Assessment LCA, as a systemic tool that has the objective of supporting the integration of sustainability on designing, innovation and the assessment of products and services. Today is a mature and standardized (ISO 14040 and ISO 14044) methodology for environmental management, especially useful for the identification of priorities and the materialization of more efficient policies.

The LCA intends to be an integrated tool for the multi-criterion assessment of products and services through its whole value chain, covering a wide variety of pressures and impacts related to human health, environment, and resources. Briefly, in the LCA the consumed resources and the emissions to air, water and soil that entails the production or use of a product or service are quantified. After that, the obtained results are translated to burdens on the areas of protection of interest, such as human health and ecosystems and resources health. This is performed using certain models with which impact indicators (e.g., ecotoxicity, human toxicity, scarcity of resources, etc.) are obtained. In summary, the LCA is a useful tool internationally adopted for assessing all the environmental issues and potential burdens. It is applied in the value chain of a product or process, including the steps of collecting, production, use and treatment of produced wastes.

Figure 3 shows the steps that integrates the LCA of a product or process, covering from the collection of the raw materials needed to the management of the wastes generated during and/or at the product end-of-life. All those stages are characterized by inputs and outputs of energy and materials flows, which is known as the Life Cycle Inventory (LCI). All inputs and outputs are associated with environmental burdens.

Due to its complexity, the LCA methodology follows a protocol established in a specific regulation defined by the ISO. According to ISO 14040: 2006, LCA is a "compilation and evaluation of the inputs, outputs and potential environmental impacts of a product system throughout its life cycle".

Figure 3 – LCA stages

The mentioned standard establishes four steps for an LCA project (Figure 4). As can be seen, it is a flexible methodology in which the different stages are interconnected with each other through information flows that can be transferred and used in any way. Thus, it is an iterative process in which it is possible to increase the level of detail of the study with each iteration.

Figure 4 – Steps of LCA methodology, according to ISO 14040

The four stages shown in Figure 4 are detailed below:

Goal and scope definition. This is the stage where it is established what objective is pursued with the development of LCA, and what information is necessary to obtain this objective. To

define the scope of the LCA two fundamental aspects must be determined: the functional unit and the system boundaries.

The functional unit (FU) acts as a reference for which all inputs and outputs of the system are normalized. It is the basis of calculation with respect to which all the flows of materials and energy that enter and leave the system and / or interconnect the unit processes included in it refer. The boundaries or limits of the system define which processes and associated flows are included within the scope of the study.

Life Cycle Inventory (LCI). In this stage, all the data are obtained and the calculation procedures necessary to identify and quantify the adverse effects on resources, environment, and human health, with respect to the functional unit are defined. Basically, it is a question of quantifying all the burdens associated with the life cycle of the product or service studied, understanding burdens as the amount of pollutants that reach the environment or resources extracted from it.

Life Cycle Impact Assessment. After the inventory analysis, the impact assessment takes place. In this stage, all the inputs and outputs identified in the inventory are related to their impact on the environment, which is quantified. ISO 14044 determines how the environmental impact assessment is structured through a series of steps, some of which are mandatory while others are optional. Figure 5 represents a scheme of this procedure.

The first step shown in Figure 5 is the selection of impact categories and indicators. An impact category represents the environmental consequences generated by the processes or systems studied. Information from the inventory within each category is used below according to the expected impact. This is the starting information used by the models to calculate the impacts of each category, for which they use characterization or equivalence factors. Each impact category has a quantitative representation called the category indicator, which is obtained by applying equivalence factors with information from the inventory. Finally, the indicators of each selected category are calculated, and the importance of potential impacts is assessed.

The selection of impact categories phase can be a bit subjective since some of them are mandatory and others optional. In response to this problem, there are available various impact assessment methodologies that define which categories to select. Some examples of methods of impact assessment are CML 2, Eco-indicator '99, ReCiPe, EIDP and EPS.

Figure 5 – Mandatory and optional elements of impact assessment, according to ISO 14042

As mentioned, there are several optional elements that facilitate the interpretation of results. The completion of these steps ultimately depends on the goal and scope of the LCA. These steps are: i) normalization, which consists in referring the quantified result of an impact category to a reference value of geographical and/or temporal level; ii) grouping, which is the classification and cataloguing of indicators and impact categories; iii) weighting, which is based on the use of factors that give a relative value to the different impact categories, so that they can be added to obtain a weighted result in the form of the only global environmental index of the system; and iv) data quality analysis, which has the objective of the reliability analysis of the LCA results. This is a mandatory stage in comparative analysis.

Interpretation of results. In this last stage, the results of the inventory analysis and the impact assessment are combined for determining in which phases or processes of the life cycle the main environmental burdens are generated. The primary objective is to determine the "hotspots" of the product or process studied from the point of view of its effect on health and the ecosystem, and with that, what points of the system can or should be improved. Moreover, it is a fundamental stage if it is desired to carry out a comparative analysis between several systems and determine which one has a better environmental performance.

4.4. Systems description

In this section, the systems to be evaluated under E-LCA study are described. These systems are the baseline and the new process proposed within the *VALUEWASTE Project*.

The baseline can be divided into several independent systems, as the end products can be obtained through different productive processes. In this case, two baseline systems will be studied: the production of proteins for humans (food) and animals (feed) and the production of mineral fertilizers.

Regarding the new processes proposed within *VALUEWASTE* solution, two main systems where biowaste is used as raw material will be studied. The first system consists in a process in which the following main biobased products are obtained: i) a single cell concentrate with high protein concentration (called single cell protein, SCP), which can be used as raw material for food and feed applications (F&F); and ii) mineral fertilizers. From this process there will also be obtained treated water and compost as by-products. The second system consists in a process in which an insect protein meal is obtained as a main biobased product, and compost as by-product.

These systems will be also assessed as one only integrated system. In this way, all the contemplated biobased products (SCP, insect protein meal and mineral fertilizers) will be obtained with a single cascade process.

The environmental assessment of all these systems is translated into the measurement of the environmental impact of each product, and with each of the production processes used.

4.4.1. Baseline system

Several baseline cases have been considered to be compared with the bioproducts obtained in *ValueWaste Project*. A general production process for the baseline cases is shown below:

a) Production of proteins for feed and food

Several production processes have been selected as representative of the baseline as all the main products obtained have a high protein content and are proper both for human and animal nutrition. The comparison among these products and the F&F products obtained with *VALUEWASTE* system will be done, in principle, on a base of the protein content of both.

Figure 6 shows the overall flowchart of the protein production, where the harvested product or the raw material are processed in order to obtain a baseline product generating, at the same time, by-products. Impact allocation methods will be considered for the obtained by-products.

Figure 6 – Overall flowchart for the considered baseline cases

b) Production of mineral fertilizers

As a biofertilizer will be obtained in *ValueWaste Project*, two subsystems to produce mineral fertilizers are considered to be compared. One of them is not industrially produced, it is assumed that it is produced by means of an acid-base reaction (struvite). The other one is currently obtained as a by-product of three chemical production processes (ammonium sulphate): i) production of acetone cyanohydrin, ii) production of caprolactam, and iii) production of acrylonitrile. Currently, it has not been decided which of these processes are going to be studied as a representative of the baseline. Probably, it will be used a mix depending on the relevance of each one in Europe. As previously said, impact allocation method must be defined if required.

4.4.2. VALUEWASTE system

The *VALUEWASTE* system considers two basic processes which use biowaste as raw material. However, these will not be described in detail because of confidential issues. On one hand, biowaste can be used in a cascade process for producing SCP for F&F applications and mineral fertilizers (struvite and ammonium sulphate). In that process, treated water and compost are also produced as by-products. On the other hand, biowaste can be used for producing insect meal, also for F&F applications (and compost as by-product).

a) Production of SCP and mineral fertilizers

In this production process, the first stage consists in the anaerobic wet digestion of the biowaste, where its organic content is partially stabilized, being produced biogas and a digestate. Each of these products is in turn the raw material of a particular value chain, with its corresponding defined biobased products.

SCP value chain. Biogas is firstly upgraded for removing the CO₂ and impurities, producing biomethane. Biomethane and other nutrients are used as a substrate methanotrophic bacteria. New biomass and other products are obtained in this step. The new biomass produced is then collected, being obtained the SCP.

Fertilizers value chain. The digestate produced in the anaerobic digestion contains a high concentration of organic matter, partially stabilised and mostly in form of suspended matter. In addition, it has a high concentration of nitrogen and phosphorus, mostly in form of dissolved compounds (ammonium and phosphate). That digestate is treated in a solid-liquid separation mechanical stage (centrifugation, screw-pressing, etc.), where suspended solids are separated from almost all the rest of the digestate. Thus, they are formed two streams: i) a drained stream (digestate liquid fraction) which contains dissolved matter, with low concentration of organic compounds and high concentration of nutrients (phosphates and ammonium), and ii) a sludge stream (digestate solid fraction), which contains the separated biomass, besides dissolved compounds which also are contained in the drained stream. These streams are used to obtain biofertilizers.

b) Production of insect meal by BSF treatment

The last of the three value chains is the F&F production by stabilizing the biowaste with insect larvae of *Hermetia illucens*, which is commonly known as "black soldier fly (BSF)". In this process, a reproductive cycle of the black soldier fly is implemented, and the biowaste is used to feed the larvae. The larvae transform the biowaste mainly into internal protein material, excreting stabilized organic matter. After the growing phase (10-16 days), insects are harvested, washed and then dried.

Therefore, there will be three systems to be studied and compared to the baseline cases from an environmental point of view. These systems will be: i) impact of insect meal obtained with biowaste, ii) impact of fertilizers and SCP obtained from biowaste, and iii) impact of all the products obtained with a cascade system in which all the initial biowaste goes to the anaerobic digestion stage.

4.5. E-LCA development approaches

Following the methodology pointed out in section 4.3, the appropriate performance of the E-LCA involves the development of the mentioned four tasks: i) goal and scope definition; ii) Life Cycle Inventory (LCI); iii) Life Cycle Impact Assessment; iv) interpretation of results.

Bearing in mind that the objective of this deliverable is to present the methodology to be followed, throughout this section it will be pointed out the starting approaches about: i) the E-LCA objective, ii) consumptions and emissions included within the studied systems, iii)

information and sources to be used in order to define the E-LCI, and iv) considered impact evaluation methods.

4.5.1. LCA Methods, goal, and scope definition

Firstly, it is important to mention that the approaches of the present report are provisional. That is to say that the approaches can be subsequently modified as a function of the information that will be finally available, and the analysis of the results obtained from the LCA calculations.

Goal. The objective of this LCA study is to determine the environmental improvement that would entail substituting the state-of-the-art production processes of the three considered products (proteins for feed and food, and fertilizers), that is, the baseline, by the new processes proposed by *VALUEWASTE* approach.

Methods. The study is divided in three phases. First, to determine the environmental impact associated with each of the three considered products, being them produced by the state-of-the-art production processes. The first system is defined hereafter as *BASELINE*. Second, to determine the environmental impact of the mentioned products, but assuming that they are produced by the new developed solutions. The second system is defined as *VALUEWASTE*. The last step consists in comparing the environmental impact of the two studied systems, *BASELINE* and *VALUEWASTE*, and determining the benefit, in environmental terms, which supposes the change in the productive model.

Scope. The scope of the LCA defines each one of the production systems previously indicated and those flows and processes which are going to be included in the environmental impact assessment. This section informs about the intended scope for each of these systems. Nevertheless, as previously mentioned, this is a starting approach and may be redefined during the LCA process.

For all systems, the type of LCA considered is “cradle-to-gate”. That is because they include all the environmental burdens, from those related to the extraction or production of all raw materials and energy sources necessary for the production process, to the flows which go to the biosphere which come from the production process or from the final treatment of the wastes generated during that process. The scope ends at the ended product at the gate of the production facilities. Therefore, it does not include the environmental burdens related to the use and end-of-life disposal phases of these products.

1) Baseline processes

Gluten meal/feed production. Figure 7 shows the scope for that baseline case. It can be seen that the system is divided in three subsystems, which are the field where maize is cultivated, the farm where it is dried and stored, and the wet mill where the gluten is produced, along with the rest of the products. It can also be seen that there are processes which take place in these places (foreground processes) and others that does not (background processes). The inputs and outputs included within the system boundary are those related to the following processes:

- Production of the mineral fertilizers used in corn cultivation. Nitrogen, phosphate, and potassium fertilizers are considered. The flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the production facilities are not included.
- Production of the pesticides used in corn cultivation. Atrazine, Glyphosate and Trichlorfon are considered. The flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the production facilities are not included.
- Production of the diesel consumed by the agricultural machinery (pumps and tractors) in corn cultivation. The flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the production facilities are not included.
- Corn cultivation. It includes all the operations done in the field (ploughing, fertilizing, seeding, irrigating, cultivation, spraying, harvesting). The inputs are fertilizers (organic and minerals), pesticides and diesel, and the output are the corn grains with 25% of H₂O, and the emission to the air, freshwater and soil of all the pollutants generated by the application of fertilizers and pesticides, and by the operation of the agricultural machinery.
- Production and distribution of the electrical energy consumed in the farm and wet mill. That energy is used for the operation of diverse machinery. the flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phase of the production and distribution facilities are not included.
- Production of the light fuel consumed in the corn drying operations that take place in the farm. The flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the production facilities are not included.
- Production of the diesel consumed by the transport media that transport the corn grains from the field to the farm, and from the farm to the wet mill. They are not included the flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the production facilities. These transport operations are considered foreground processes which are included in farm and wet mill subsystems, respectively.

Figure 7 – Flowchart of the baseline system (gluten feed/meal production) displaying the boundaries, processes, and flows

- Corn conditioning. It includes the transport of the corn grains from the field to the farm, and all the operations done in the farm (cleaning, drying, and storing). The inputs are the cultivated corn grains, and the rest of raw materials and energy flows. The outputs are the corn grains with 12% of H₂O, and the emission to the air, freshwater and soil of all the pollutants generated in conditioning operations.
- Production of the SO₂ consumed in the wet mill. The flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the production facilities are not included.
- Production of the tap water consumed in the wet mill. That is produced in an external facility (water treatment plant) from groundwater. The flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the production facilities are not included.
- Production of the natural gas consumed in the wet mill operations. The flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the production facilities are not included.
- Corn meal production. It includes the transport of the corn grains from the farm to the mill, and all the operations done in the wet mill. The inputs are the dried corn grains, and the rest of raw materials and energy flows. The outputs are the different products and by-products (gluten meal, corn starch, etc.), produced wastewater, and the emission to the air, freshwater and soil of all the pollutants generated in conditioning operations. For the product's impacts quantification, price allocation is applied. The produced wastewater remains in technosphere and is treated afterwards.
- Treatment of the wastewaters produced in the wet mill. Wastewater has a low organic load, so it is considered that can be directly discharged into sewer, being treated afterwards in a municipal wastewater treatment plant. the flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the treatment facilities, as well as the distribution facilities are not included.

Outside the system boundary it can be found: i) the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the agricultural machinery, conditioning facilities, wet mill facilities, and the production facilities of the background processes, ii) transport operations of all the consumables except the grain transport, iii) construction and end-of-life of the transport media used to transport the corn to the farm and to the mill, iv) organic N fertilizer (cattle manure) production, as this is a by-product of the meat/milk production.

Soybean meal production. Figure 8 shows the scope for that baseline case. The system is divided in two subsystems, which are the field where soy is cultivated, and the wet mill where the soy bean meal is produced, along with the rest of the products.

Figure 8 – Flowchart of the baseline system (soy bean meal production) displaying the boundaries, processes, and flows

The inputs and outputs included within the system boundary are those related to the following processes:

- Production of the mineral fertilizers used in soy cultivation. Nitrogen, phosphate, and potassium fertilizers are considered. the flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the production facilities are not included.
- Production of the pesticides used in soy cultivation. Thifensulfuron-methyl and Triflural are considered. The flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the production facilities are not included.

- Production of the diesel consumed by the agricultural machinery (pumps and tractors) in soy cultivation. The flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the production facilities are not included.
- Soy bean cultivation. It includes all the operations done in the field (ploughing, fertilizing, seeding, irrigating, cultivation, spraying, harvesting). The inputs are fertilizers, pesticides and diesel, and the output are the soy beans with 12% of H₂O, and the emission to the air, freshwater and soil of all the pollutants generated by the application of fertilizers and pesticides, and by the operation of the agricultural machinery.
- Production of the cyclohexane consumed in the wet mill. The flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the production facilities are not included.
- Production of the tap water consumed in the wet mill. That is produced from surface water. The flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the production facilities are not included.
- Production of heavy fuel consumed for heat production in the wet mill operations. The flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the production facilities are not included.
- Production of the natural gas consumed in wet mill operations. It is used for heat and electricity production. The flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the production facilities are not included.
- Production of the diesel consumed by the transport media that transport the soybeans from the field to the wet mill. The flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the production facilities are not included. These transport operations are considered foreground processes which are included in wet mill subsystems.
- Soybean meal production. It includes the transport of the soybeans from the farm to the mill, and all the operations done in the wet mill. The inputs are the soybeans, and the rest of raw materials and energy flows. The outputs are the different products and by-products (soybean meal, hulls, and oil), and the emission to the air, freshwater and soil of all the pollutants generated in conditioning operations. For the product's impacts quantification, price allocation is applied

Outside the system boundary it can be found: i) the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the agricultural machinery, wet mill facilities, and the production facilities of the background processes, ii) transport operations of all the consumables except soy beans, iii) construction and

end-of-life disposal phases of the transport media used to transport the soy beans to the wet mill, iv) Organic N fertilizer (cattle manure) production, as this is a by-product of the meat/milk production.

Whey protein production. Figure 9 shows the scope for that one of the baseline cases. The system is divided in two subsystems, which are the farm, where milk is produced, and the dairy factory, where the whey protein is produced, along with the rest of products (cheese and curd).

Figure 9 – Flowchart of the baseline system (whey protein production) displaying the boundaries, processes, and flows

The inputs and outputs included within the system boundary are those related to the following processes:

- Production of the tap water consumed in the farm. It is produced in situ from groundwater. The flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the production facilities are not included.
- Production and distribution of the electrical energy consumed in the farm and dairy factory. That energy is used for the operation of diverse machinery. In factory subsystem, it is only

considered the electricity consumed in the whey protein production from whey, since that is a separate production line from the rest. The flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phase of the production and distribution facilities are not included.

- Production of the diesel consumed by the agricultural machinery in farm and by the transport media which transport the milk from farm to dairy factory. The flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the production facilities are not included. These operations (agricultural and transport activities) are considered foreground processes which are included in farm and dairy factory, respectively.
- Milk production. It includes all the operations done in the farm, such as the agricultural activities for fodder production, livestock feeding and manure management. Farm produces two types of products, which are the milk and the new livestock for meat production, but only the impacts related to the milk production are considered. For doing that, it has been considered an allocation based on energy required for growth vs energy required for milk production. Furthermore, the manure is valorised in the farm itself. The liquid manure is used as source of nitrogen for soil fertilizing. Solid fraction is used for biogas production, which is valorised in the farm. So, the inputs are the water consumed by livestock and the rest of raw materials and energy flows. The outputs are the milk, and the emissions to the air, freshwater and soil of all the pollutants generated in farm operations.
- Production of the bacteria consumed in the dairy factory. The flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the production facilities are not included.
- Production of the natural gas consumed in dairy factory. It is only included the gas consumed in the whey protein production, since that is a separate production line from the rest. In that case, it is used for producing the thermal energy needed for concentrating the protein solution by evaporation and spray-drying. The flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the production facilities are not included.
- Whey protein production. It includes all the operations done in the dairy factory, besides milk transport operation, which is considered a foreground process included in this subsystem. Factory produces cheese/curd as products and whey as by-product. Whey protein is produced from whey. For calculating the impact of the produced whey in the cheese production stage it is assumed a mass allocation. In the subsequent stage of whey protein production, there is not impact allocation, since it is a production line separated from the rest, with its own consumptions and emissions. The inputs are the milk coming from the farm and the rest of the raw materials and energy flows. The outputs are the solid

whey protein (as the cheese impact is not accounted), wastewater, and the emissions to the air, freshwater and soil of all the pollutants generated in factory operations. The produced wastewater remains in technosphere and is treated afterwards.

- Treatment of the wastewaters produced in the dairy factory. Without its protein content, it is supposed that wastewater has a low organic load, so it is considered that can be directly discharged into sewer, being treated afterwards in a municipal wastewater treatment plant. The flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the treatment facilities, as well as the distribution facilities are not included.

Outside the system boundary it can be found: i) the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the farm and dairy factory facilities, and the production facilities of the background processes, ii) transport operations of all the consumables, except milk, and iii) construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the transport media used to transport the milk to the factory.

Synthetic struvite production. Figure 10 shows the scope for that one of the baseline cases. The system is divided in three subsystems, which are the facilities for $Mg(OH)_2$, $(NH_4)_2HPO_4$ and struvite production. The inputs and outputs included within the system boundary are those related to the following processes:

- Production of the washed limestone consumed in the $Ca(OH)_2$ production. They are not included the flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the production facilities.
- Production of the refractory bricks consumed in the $Ca(OH)_2$ production. They are used as refractory material in the limestone calcination furnace. The flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the production facilities are not included.
- Production and distribution of the electrical energy consumed in the three production systems. That energy is used for the operation of diverse machinery. The flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phase of the production and distribution facilities are not included.
- Production of fuels consumed in the $Ca(OH)_2$ production. It is considered propane, light fuel oil, heavy fuel oil, lignite, hard coal, and coke. Natural gas is used too but is not included and is referred in a subsequent point. The flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the production facilities are not included.

Figure 10 – Flowchart of the baseline system (synthetic struvite production) displaying the boundaries, processes, and flows

- Production and distribution of the natural gas consumed in the three production systems. The flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phase of the production and distribution facilities are not included.
- Ca(OH)_2 production. It includes all the operations done in the production facilities. The inputs are CaCO_3 , refractory bricks, surface water, fuels, and electricity. The outputs are the solid Ca(OH)_2 , produced wastewater and the emissions to the air, freshwater and soil of all the pollutants generated in factory operations. Regarding wastewater, it remains in the technosphere and is treated afterwards. Finally, the flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the production facilities are not included.
- Treatment of the wastewaters produced in the Ca(OH)_2 factory. It is assumed that the wastewater is treated in the own facility. They are not included the flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the treatment facilities, as well as the distribution facilities.
- Mg(OH)_2 production. It includes all the operations done in the production facilities. The inputs are Ca(OH)_2 , seawater, surface water, natural gas, and electricity. The output is the solid Mg(OH)_2 and the emissions to the air of all the pollutants generated in factory operations. The flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the production facilities are not included.
- Production of the H_3PO_4 consumed in the $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{HPO}_4$ production. The flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the production facilities are not included.
- Production of the NH_3 consumed in the $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{HPO}_4$ production. It is considered the Haber-Bosch production process. The flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the production facilities are not included. It is also included the NH_3 transport to the $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{HPO}_4$ production facilities. In transport processes the flows related to the production of consumed fuels, as well as the transport emissions are included. On the other hand, the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the transport media are not included.
- Diammonium phosphate production. It includes all the operations done in the production facilities. The inputs are phosphoric acid, ammonia, natural gas, and electricity. The outputs are the solid $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{HPO}_4$ and the emissions to the air, freshwater and soil of all the pollutants generated in factory operations. The flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the production facilities are not included.
- Production of the NaOH consumed in the struvite production. The flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the production facilities are not included.

- Synthetic struvite production. It includes all the operations done in the production facilities. As there are not references of industrial processes for producing this kind of product, an acid-base reaction system in aqueous phase is assumed, and subsequent precipitation, filtering and drying of the salt formed. The inputs are magnesium hydroxide, diammonium phosphate, caustic soda, natural gas (for final product drying) and electricity (mixing, filtering, and final drying). The outputs are the solid struvite and the emissions to the air of all the pollutants generated in the production process. The flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the production facilities are not included.

Outside the system boundary it can be found: i) the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of all the production & distribution facilities (both foreground and background processes), ii) the transport operations of all the consumables (except for NH_3 transport), and iii) the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the transport media used to transport NH_3 to diammonium phosphate factory.

Ammonium sulphate production. Figures 11, 12 and 13 show the scope for the ammonium sulphate production, differing among them according to the applied production process.

Figure 11 shows the scope for the ammonium sulphate production (acetone cyanohydrin production where ammonium sulphate is obtained as by-product). The inputs and outputs included within the system boundary are those related to the following processes:

- Production of the chemicals consumed in acetone cyanohydrin production factory. These chemicals are acetone, ammonia, and sulphuric acid. The flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the production facilities are not included.
- Production and distribution to the consumer of the natural gas consumed in the factory. The flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phase of the production and distribution facilities are not included.
- Production and distribution to the consumer of the electrical energy consumed in the factory. The flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phase of the production and distribution facilities are not included.
- Ammonium sulphate production. It includes all the operations done in the factory. The inputs are the chemicals (acetone, NH_3 , H_2SO_4), and energy flows (natural gas and electricity). The outputs are the main products (ammonium sulphate and acetone cyanohydrin), the fuel gas and wastewater, and the emissions to the air, freshwater and soil of all the pollutants generated in factory operations. Regarding the main products, no allocation methods is applied. Regarding

fuel gas and wastewater, both remains in technosphere and are valorised/treated afterwards. Finally, the flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the production facilities are not included.

- Energy valorisation. The fuel gas which is produced in the ammonium sulphate production process is consumed for thermal energy production. That entails savings in fuels which would be necessary to produce for generating an equivalent amount of energy, as well as emissions to the air derived to the gas natural gas combustion. The flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phase of the energy valorisation facilities are not included.

Figure 11 – Flowchart of the baseline system (ammonium sulphate by-product of acetone cyanohydrin production) displaying the boundaries, processes, and flows

- Production and distribution of natural gas avoided. As mentioned, energy valorisation of the fuel gas entails savings in fuels production. If as that fuel it is considered natural gas, the savings can be calculated in terms of natural gas production. Regarding distribution, it is assumed that the fuel gas consumption point is the same than its production point. The flows related to the

construction and end-of-life disposal phase of the production and distribution facilities are not included.

- Treatment of wastewaters produced in the factory. The flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the treatment facilities, as well as the distribution facilities are not included.

Outside the system boundary it can be found: i) the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of all the production and distribution facilities (both foreground and background processes), ii) construction and end-of-life disposal phases of facilities for distribution of natural gas and electricity, iii) transport operations of all the consumables (acetone, NH_3 , H_2SO_4).

Figure 12 shows the scope for the ammonium sulphate production (caprolactam production where ammonium sulphate is obtained as by-product). The inputs and outputs included within the system boundary are those related to the following processes:

- Production of the cyclohexane consumed in caprolactam factory. Cyclohexane is used for producing cyclohexanone by oxidation with O_2 . The flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the cyclohexane production facilities are not included.
- Production of the O_2 consumed in factory. Pure oxygen is used for producing cyclohexanone and also for producing hydroxylamine. They are not included the flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the O_2 production facilities.
- Production of the N_2 consumed in factory. Nitrogen is used for producing hydroxylamine, along with ammonia and O_2 . The flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the N_2 production facilities are not included.
- Production of the deionised water consumed in factory. Deionised water is used in several reactions and processes. It is produced in situ from tap water. The flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the production and distribution facilities are not included.
- Production of the NH_3 consumed in factory. Ammonia is used for producing hydroxylamine, along with N_2 and O_2 and also in caprolactam production. The flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the ammonia production facilities are not included.

Figure 12 – Flowchart of the baseline system (ammonium sulphate by-product of caprolactam) displaying the boundaries, processes, and flows

- Production of the H₂SO₄ consumed in factory. Sulphuric acid is used in caprolactam production. The flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the H₂SO₄ production facilities are not included.
- Production and distribution to the consumer of the electrical energy consumed in the factory. The flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phase of the production and distribution facilities are not included.
- Production and distribution to the consumer of the light fuel consumed in the factory. It is used for producing process steam. The flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phase of the production facilities are not included.
- Ammonium sulphate production. It includes all the operations done in the factory. The inputs are the chemicals (cyclohexane, NH₃, H₂SO₄), O₂, N₂, deionised water, and energy flows (natural gas and electricity). The outputs are the main products (ammonium sulphate and caprolactam), and the emissions to the air, freshwater and soil of all the pollutants generated in factory operations.

Regarding the main products, the allocation is based on the market price. Finally, the flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the production facilities are not included.

Outside the system boundary it can be found: i) the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of all the production and distribution facilities (both foreground and background processes), ii) transport operations of all the consumables (cyclohexane, O₂, light fuel-oil, etc.).

Figure 13 shows the scope for the ammonium sulphate production (acrylonitrile production where ammonium sulphate is obtained as by-product). The inputs and outputs included within the system boundary are those related to the following processes:

- Production of the chemicals consumed in acrylonitrile factory. These chemicals are propene, ammonia, and sulphuric acid. They are not included the flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the production facilities.
- Production of the deionised water consumed in factory. Deionised water is produced in situ from tap water and is used for process steam production. The flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the production facilities are not included.
- Production of the natural gas consumed in the factory. The flows related to distribution operations as well as the construction and end-of-life disposal phase of the production and distribution facilities are not included.
- Production and distribution to the consumer of the electrical energy consumed in the factory. The flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phase of the production and distribution facilities are not included.
- Ammonium sulphate production. It includes all the operations done in the factory. The inputs are the chemicals (propene, NH₃, H₂SO₄), deionised water, and energy flows (natural gas and electricity). The outputs are the main products (acrylonitrile, ammonium sulphate and hydrocyanic acid), wastewater and solid wastes (hazardous and non-hazardous), and the emissions to the air, freshwater and soil of all the pollutants generated in factory operations. Regarding the products, price allocation is applied. Regarding wastes and wastewater, both remains in technosphere and are valorised / treated afterwards. Finally, the flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the production facilities are not included.

Figure 13 – Flowchart of the baseline system (ammonium sulphate and hydrocyanic acid by-products of acrylonitrile production) displaying the boundaries, processes, and flows

- Treatment of wastewaters produced in the factory. It is considered that wastewater has low organic load, so it can be directly discharged into sewer, being treated afterwards in a municipal wastewater treatment plant. The flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the distribution and treatment facilities are not included.
- Treatment of non-hazardous wastes. The treatment is done in a municipal waste incineration plant. The flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the distribution and treatment facilities are not included.
- Treatment of hazardous wastes. The treatment consists of vitrification, followed by macro-encapsulation and finally landfilling. There is no energy recovery. The flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the distribution and treatment facilities.

Outside the system boundary it can be found: i) the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of all the production and distribution facilities (both foreground and background processes), ii) construction and end-of-life disposal phases of facilities for distribution of natural gas and electricity, iii) transport operations of all the consumables (propene, ammonia, sulphuric acid, natural gas, etc.), iv) Transport operations of all generated wastes & wastewaters from factory to the treatment facilities.

2) Valuwaste processes

The processes integrating the *VALUEWASTE* system are described in the present sub-section. These are represented separately according to each of the three products which are intended to obtain.

Biobased fertilizers production. The system is divided in different processes implemented in a same location. These processes produce fertilizers, together with compost and treated water, suitable for being discharged to the biosphere. Additionally, the system has two outputs (biogas and solid fraction of digestate), which would connect with the two remaining biobased products production processes.

An important consideration to mention is that biowaste could be initially pre-treated by a mechanical treatment for separating inappropriate materials, such as glass or plastics. This is the same step in the first stage of mechanical-biological treatment plants of municipal solid waste (MSW), which produces OFMSW from MSW. Then, the OFMSW is used to obtain compost. If the waste separation in households was properly done, these inappropriate materials would not be present in the biowaste, which is one of the fundamental premises of the *VALUEWASTE Project*, in accordance with European policies. Due to biowaste should not contain inappropriate materials, and to the fact that the current percentage of these materials in the MSW or biowaste are very variable depending on the city, and the expected environmental impact is low as compared with the rest of the treatment stages, it has been decided to leave that pretreatment stage outside the limits of the studied system.

Other issue that is important to mention is that the composting stage included in the assessment is not included in the treatment plant of the project. The reason is that it is a well-known technology which is not necessary to study or assess, although afterwards it would be convenient to include when implementing the whole system at industrial scale. It is important to bear in mind that the solid fraction of the digestate could also be applied directly in agricultural soil, without being composted, because it comes from an anaerobic treatment stage, where the organic matter is partially stabilised.

The inputs and outputs included within the system boundary are those related to the following processes:

- Production of softened water. It is used to replenish the water purges done in the biogas boiler. The normal procedure would be to use tap water, and then soft it in situ by an ionic exchange process. In this case, tap water production would be a background process, and softened water production would be a foreground process done in the production facilities. The flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the production facilities are not included.
- Production of chemicals used in the process and equipment cleaning. The chemicals required to perform the different step within the production of biofertilizers will be taking into account. The flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the production facilities are not included.
- Production and distribution of the electrical energy consumed in the production facilities. The flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phase of the production and distribution facilities are not included.
- Production and distribution of the diesel consumed in the production facilities. Diesel has been selected because municipal solid waste treatment plants are usually far away from urban or industrial areas, in locations where it is unusual for a natural gas (less polluting) grid to reach. Flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phase of the production and distribution facilities are not included.
- Production of the tap water consumed in the production facilities. The flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the production and distribution facilities are not included.
- Anaerobic digestion. Consumptions and emissions are included. The treatment and valorisation of the biogas for heat production in boiler are also included in the studied system. The inputs are biowaste (returned liquid digestate is not considered, as it conforms a recirculation loop), softened water used in boiler, and energy flows (electricity and diesel). The flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the production facilities are not included.
- Solid-liquid separation of digestate. The inputs like digestate and the electricity consumed by the separation equipment are included. Outputs are the solid and liquid fractions of the digestate, which go to the processes of composting and struvite production, respectively. Direct emissions for this process are not considered. The flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the separation facilities are not included.
- Compost production. The inputs of the process are the solid fraction of the digestate and the energy flows. The outputs are the end product (compost) and the emissions to the air, freshwater

and soil of all the pollutants generated in the process. The flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the production facilities are not included.

- Struvite production. Different chemicals are used to precipitate struvite, which will be the inputs of this process, besides digestate and energy flows (electricity and diesel). Outputs are the dried struvite precipitate, liquid fraction of digestate which has been removed its P content and part of its N content, and the emissions to the air, freshwater and soil of all the pollutants generated in the process. The flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the production facilities are not included.
- Ammonium sulphate production. Remaining NH_3 within the effluent coming from the struvite production process is transform into $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$. Afterwards, this salt is concentrated and dried. All inputs and outputs (emissions to the air, freshwater and soil of all the pollutants generated in the process) are considered. The flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the production facilities are not included.
- Application of produced compost as fertilizer. The solid fraction of the digestate has available N and P in its composition and it can be used in agriculture as fertilizer after being composted. That supposes savings in mineral fertilizers production. The composting process includes the consumptions of the machinery used in the compost application, as well as the emissions to the air, water and soil which take place in the fertilizing operations. The flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the agricultural machinery used in compost application are not included.
- Avoided production of mineral fertilizers. The application of compost in agricultural soil supposes savings in the production of mineral fertilizers. The flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phase of the fertilizers production facilities are not included.

Outside the system boundary it can be found different terms, such as construction and end-of-life disposal phases of all the production and distribution facilities (both foreground and background processes) and transport of the compost to the application site.

Production of F&F ingredients (dried SCP). The inputs and outputs included within the system boundary are those related to the following processes:

- Production of the activated carbon and its treatment once exhausted. It is used in a first step before producing the SCP. Once it is exhausted, it will be treated in an external facility. The flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the production/treatment facilities are not included.

- Production and distribution of the electrical energy consumed. It will be taken into account all the electricity consumed by the equipment such as pumps, compressors and cooling systems. The flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phase of the production and distribution facilities are not included.
- Production of the O₂ consumed in the SCP production. There are available different options to produce the O₂. Among them, the best option will be selected to be included in the system to be evaluated. The selection will be done based on previous analysis. The flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the production facilities are not included.
- Production of the chemicals consumed in the SCP production. It will be included both macro and micro nutrients which are necessary for the fermentation process, besides the chemicals for pH adjustment. The flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the chemicals production facilities are not included.
- Production and distribution to the consumer of the diesel consumed in the facilities of SCP production. The diesel is used for thermal energy production and, thus, used in several processes of the facility. Its consumption in all equipment will be considered. The flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phase of the production and distribution facilities are not included.
- SCP production. The inputs are the leftover biogas coming from the anaerobic digester, O₂, mentioned chemicals, and energy flows (natural gas and electricity). The outputs are the SCP, wastewater and the emissions to the air, freshwater and soil of all the pollutants generated in factory operations. The flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the production facilities are not included.
- Treatment of produced wastewaters. The produced wastewater comes from the purges which are periodically done in the fermenter for avoiding the accumulation of solutes inside it. Flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the distribution and wastewater treatment facilities are not included.

Outside the system boundary it can be found, for instance, the transport operations of all the consumables and the production and transport of bacteria used for the fermentation.

Production of Food & Feed grade protein (insect protein). The inputs and outputs included within the system boundary are those related to the following processes:

- Production of the tap water consumed in the production facilities. The flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the production and distribution facilities are not included.
- Production of the softened water consumed in the production facilities. The softened water will be obtained from surface water. The flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the production facilities are not included.
- Production of the chemicals consumed. The flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the production and distribution facilities are not included.
- Production and distribution of the electrical energy consumed in the production facilities. This energy is used for the operation of diverse machinery and equipment. The flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phase of the production and distribution facilities are not included.
- Production and distribution to the consumer of the diesel consumed in the production facilities. Diesel is used for thermal energy production for producing steam. The flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phase of the production and distribution facilities are not included.
- Insect meal production. The inputs are the biowaste and/or solid fraction of the digestate, tap water and softened water, chemicals and energy flows (natural gas and electricity). The outputs are the insect meal, compost (stabilized biowaste), produced wastewater and emissions to the air, freshwater and soil of all the pollutants generated in production facilities. Wastewater remains in technosphere and is treated afterwards. The flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the production facilities are not included.
- Application of produced compost as fertilizer. The stabilized biowaste and/or solid digestate obtained as by-product has available N and P in its composition, so they can be used in agriculture as fertilizer. That supposes savings in mineral fertilizers production. That process includes the consumptions of the machinery used in the compost application, as well as the emissions to the air, water and soil which takes place in the fertilizing operations. The flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the agricultural machinery used in compost application are not included.
- Avoided production of mineral fertilizers. The application of compost in agriculture supposes savings in the production of mineral fertilizers. The flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phase of the fertilizers production facilities are not included.

- Treatment of produced wastewaters. Wastewater are generated in, for instance, cleaning of facilities or purges of water tanks. The flows related to the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the distribution and wastewater treatment facilities are not included.

Outside the system boundary it can be found, for instance, the compost transportation from the production facilities to the application site and the construction and end-of-life disposal phases of the agricultural machinery used for compost applying.

Functional unit. Once the limits of the system are defined, the following step is to select the functional unit (FU). The FU is the quantification of an input or output flow which serves as a reference for all the inputs and outputs. So, the purpose of setting a FU is to define a reference for all the inputs and outputs of the system, which is necessary for assuring the representativity of the system, and the comparability among systems. Considering the goal of the study, the FU selected is the kilogram of product at the gates of the production facility. The considered products are: i) proteins produced by each of the three processes considered, ii) synthetic struvite, ii) ammonium sulphate.

4.5.2. Life Cycle Inventory

Life cycle inventory (LCI) analysis involves the creation of an inventory of flows from and to the biosphere for a product system. Inventory flows include inputs of water, energy and raw materials, and releases to air, soil, and water. The input and output data needed for the construction of the model are collected for all activities within the system boundary. It is worth highlighting that these data must be related to the functional unit defined in the goal and scope definition.

Material and energy flows and calculation parameters used in the development of the Life Cycle Inventories of the described processes, as well as the considered references, are described below.

a) Baseline system

Gluten meal. At first, the inputs and outputs of the following processes included in the GaBi software database, will be used to determine the environmental burdens linked to the considered product.

- *EU-28_Corn grains, at farm (12% H₂O content); technology mix; production mix, at plant; 12 % H₂O.* More information can be found in: <http://gabi-documentation-2020.gabi-software.com/xml-data/processes/fa8c89d3-2dce-414d-aff-3b0fef3be636.xml>
- *EU-28_Gluten meal (corn wet mill) (economic allocation) - open input corn seeds; corn wet milling; single producer, at plant; corn gluten meal.* More information in: <http://gabi->

documentation-2020.gabi-software.com/xml-data/processes/1f908b8f-7ed9-4f4d-a90d-9fdeb2412de7.xml

Soybean meal. Initially, the inputs and outputs of the following processes included in the GaBi ts software database, will be used to determine the environmental burdens linked to the considered product.

- *EU-28_Soybean meal (wet mill) (economic allocation); soybean cultivation and wet mill with pressing and solvent extraction; production mix, at plant; Soybean meal hexane extracted (48% PC)*. More information in: <http://gabi-documentation-2020.gabi-software.com/xml-data/processes/99ee5a8d-6d16-4b36-a71e-cb5f3b8049e9.xml>

Whey protein concentrate. At first, the inputs and outputs of the following processes included in the GaBi ts software database, will be used to determine the environmental burdens linked to the considered product.

- *DE_Milk (at farm); Operating facilities, livestock husbandry, milking; single producer, at plant; 1 kg raw milk, 88% H₂O*. More information in: <http://gabi-documentation-2020.gabi-software.com/xml-data/processes/15da1281-aa56-4524-8e72-a0dd686224dd.xml>
- *US_Whey protein concentrate (powder); milk Pretreatment, processing of curd and whey, ultrafiltration, evaporation, spray drying; production mix, at plant; 22% carbon content*. More information can be found in: <http://gabi-documentation-2020.gabi-software.com/xml-data/processes/bacbd813-146d-45ae-90ab-7c01e5d5931e.xml>

Synthetic struvite. The inventory is composed by the flows corresponding to several processes included in the GaBi ts software database, as well as others obtained from bibliographic references and / or theoretical calculation factors. According to the Figure 15, the processes are as follows:

- Ca(OH)_2 consumption. In this case, to gather all the resources consumption, as well as emissions to air, water, and soil that the Ca(OH)_2 consumption process entails, the following process included in the databases of the GaBi software is taken.
 - *DE_Calcium hydroxide (Ca(OH)_2 ; dry; slaked lime) (EN15804 A1-A3); technology mix; production mix, at plant; solid, density: 2,24 g·cm⁻³ (20 °C), molar mass: 74,10 g·mol⁻¹*. More information can be found in: <http://gabi-documentation-2020.gabi-software.com/xml-data/processes/63fbbb79-50aa-4e3f-a2cc-29ac76f51182.xml>
- Other possible consumptions in Mg(OH)_2 production. There are also consumptions of seawater, which is not considered in the inventory as it is assumed to be renewable, as well as freshwater

and H_2SO_4 that are used to purify the obtained $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$. The flows of these two raw materials and the possible wastewater stream generated in the purification stage have not been included for the moment. The possible inclusion of these flows in the inventory will depend on the availability of information about their quantities.

- Energy consumption in $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$ production. It is assumed that the precipitate formed in $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$ is decanted, and that the extracted sludge is dewatered by a mechanical procedure such as centrifugation or vacuum filtration, which entails electrical energy consumption. It is assumed that the dewatered sludge is subsequently dried by a process that consumes both electrical and thermal energy, such as a rotating drum with hot air drying. For heat generation, the on-site consumption of natural gas in a boiler (85% efficiency) has been considered. The consumption of both electricity and natural gas has not been defined, since the dewatering and drying technologies that are going to be included have not been defined yet. Therefore, the relationship between kWh of electricity and / or gas consumed per litre of separated water is not known at the moment. When these technologies are defined and the dry matter content of the precipitated and dewatered sludges, ratios become available and the consumption will be calculated. Once the electricity and natural gas consumptions are defined, they will be taken to the following processes included in databases of the GaBi software for determining the related environmental burdens.
 - *EU-28_Electricity grid mix 1kV-60kV; AC, technology mix; consumption mix, to consumer; 1kV - 60kV.* More information can be found in: <http://gabi-documentation-2020.gabi-software.com/xml-data/processes/0a1b40db-5645-4db8-a887-eb09300b7b74.xml>
 - *EU-28_Natural gas mix; technology mix; consumption mix, to consumer; medium pressure level (< 1 bar).* More information can be found in: <http://gabi-documentation-2020.gabi-software.com/xml-data/processes/c6387e19-933f-4726-a7ad-7a8050aa418c.xml>
- Emissions to the atmosphere in $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$ production. At the moment, only the emissions to the air due to the consumption of the natural gas in boiler in the own factory will be considered to produce the necessary heat for $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$ drying. For calculating these emissions, the methods described in MAPAMA and IPCC will be considered (IPCC, 2006, MAPAMA, 2020).
- $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$ consumption. As indicated above, the $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$ production process consists of adding $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ to seawater to precipitate $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$, since Mg is more insoluble than Ca. For determining the consumption of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$, it is initially assumed that the moles of magnesium which precipitate are equal to those of calcium added.

- $(\text{NH}_2)\text{HPO}_4$ consumption. In this case, to gather all the resource consumption, as well as emissions to air, water, and soil that the production process entails, the following process included in the databases of the GaBi software is taken.

- *EU-28_Diammonium phosphate (DAP, 18% N, 46% P₂O₅); neutralising phosphoric acid with ammonia, including primary production; production mix, at plant; 18% nitrogen, 46% phosphate.* More information in: <http://gabi-documentation-2020.gabi-software.com/xml-data/processes/3e10ae2e-01f5-4e91-b098-8f9b4b44e119.xml>

As the synthetic struvite production process does not exist at an industrial level, it has been assumed that struvite is obtained by an acid-base reaction adding diammonium phosphate, magnesium hydroxide and sodium hydroxide, all in solid phase, in deionised water. To determine the consumptions, a stoichiometric reaction is assumed, and the following reagent concentrations: $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$ and NaOH , 100% and diammonium phosphate with N18% and P_2O_5 46%. To confirm the NaOH that must be added and the struvite production yields, chemical precipitation tests at laboratory-scale will be carried out with these three reagents, at constant temperature and pH. It is not foreseen to include the consumption of deionized water in the process, although this may vary depending on the results obtained in the laboratory tests.

- NaOH consumption. In this case, to gather all the resources consumption, as well as emissions to air, water, and soil that the production process entails, the following process included in the databases of the GaBi software is taken.

- *EU-28_Sodium hydroxide (caustic soda) mix (100%); technology mix; production mix, at plant;*
1. More information available in <http://gabi-documentation-2020.gabi-software.com/xml-data/processes/8034f0ff-d0b9-47a8-86e8-ec772f56871.xml>

- Energy consumption in struvite production. Similar to $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$, it is assumed that the formed precipitate of struvite is concentrated by settling and dewatering and is finally dried. Similarly, the ratios of natural gas and electricity consumption per volume of separated or evaporated water have not been defined for the moment. Depending on the results obtained in the laboratory chemical precipitation tests that are going to be done, as well as the drying technologies that are going to be proposed, the aforementioned consumptions will be calculated. For determining the environmental burdens related to electricity and natural gas consumption, they will be taken the following processes included in databases of the GaBi software.

- *EU-28_Electricity grid mix 1kV-60kV; AC, technology mix; consumption mix, to consumer; 1kV - 60kV.* More information can be found in: <http://gabi-documentation-2020.gabi-software.com/xml-data/processes/0a1b40db-5645-4db8-a887-eb09300b7b74.xml>
 - *EU-28_Natural gas mix; technology mix; consumption mix, to consumer; medium pressure level (< 1 bar).* More information can be found in: <http://gabi-documentation-2020.gabi-software.com/xml-data/processes/c6387e19-933f-4726-a7ad-7a8050aa418c.xml>
- Emissions to the atmosphere in struvite production. For the moment, only the emissions to the air due to the consumption of the natural gas in boiler, in the own factory, to produce the necessary heat for $\text{NH}_4\text{MgPO}_4 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ drying will be considered. For calculating these emissions, the methods described in MAPAMA and IPCC will be considered (IPCC, 2006, MAPAMA, 2020).

Ammonium sulphate. Initially, the inputs and outputs of the following processes included in the GaBi software database, will be used to determine the environmental burdens linked to the considered product.

- *EU-28_Ammonium sulphate (co product Acetone cyanohydrin); with hydrogen cyanide from acrylonitrile by-product; single route, at plant; 1.77 g/cm³, 132.14 g/mol.* More information in: <http://gabi-documentation-2020.gabi-software.com/xml-data/processes/6185baf0-970e-4f38-93f3-85e1085d4f8a.xml>
- *DE_Ammonium sulphate (Caprolactam production); propene ammoxidation; production mix, at plant; solid, density: 1,77 g·cm⁻³, molar mass: 132,14 g·mol⁻¹.* More information available in: <http://gabi-documentation-2020.gabi-software.com/xml-data/processes/76f6c5a3-fa91-4e57-9ee9-3ed05fe52b02.xml>
- *DE_Ammonium sulphate, by product acrylonitrile, hydrocyanic acid; propene ammoxidation, by-product acrylonitrile; single route, at plant; 1.77 g/cm³, 132.14 g/mol.* More information in: <http://gabi-documentation-2020.gabi-software.com/xml-data/processes/fdaa86db-76bb-4513-85f3-0ee823bced64.xml>

b) VALUEWASTE system

The inventory data used in the VALUEWASTE systems will be composed of foreground and background data. The foreground data will be obtained from the experimental phase of the VALUEWASTE Project, that is, from the operation of the pilot plants. The background data will be composed by processes included in the GaBi software, and also by information obtained from bibliographic technical sources.

Biobased fertilizers. Information about material and energy flows and calculation parameters that are going to be used in the development of the Life Cycle Inventory of the process, as well as the considered bibliographic references are described below.

- Softened water consumption. This data will be estimated in the implementation phase of the *VALUEWASTE Project* from the exploitation data of the pilot plant. For determining the environmental burdens related to softened water consumption, the following process included in databases of the GaBi software will be taken.
 - *EU-28_Process water; ion exchange, from surface water; single route, at plant; 1000 kg/m³, 18 g/mol*. More information available in: <http://gabi-documentation-2020.gabi-software.com/xml-data/processes/db009016-338f-11dd-bd11-0800200c9a66.xml>
- Chemical consumption. The needed amounts of chemicals will be defined in the experimental phase of the project and will be contrasted with information from bibliographic sources. For determining the environmental burdens related to chemical consumption, some processes included in databases of the GaBi software will be taken. For instance:
 - *EU-28_Acrylonitrile (AN); propene ammoxidation, by- product ammonium sulphate; production mix, at plant; 0.81 g/cm³, 53.06 g/mol (en)*. More information available in: <http://gabi-documentation-2020.gabi-software.com/xml-data/processes/152eaca8-9662-47be-94d2-4711a042b51e.xml>
- Tap water consumption. The tap water volumes consumed in each stage of the production process will be determined in the implementation phase of the *VALUEWASTE Project* from the exploitation data of the pilot plant. For determining the environmental burdens related to tap water consumption, the following process included in databases of the GaBi software will be taken.
 - *EU-28_Tap water from surface water; filtration, disinfection, ion removal etc., from surface water; production mix, at plant; 1000 kg/m³, 18 g/mol*. More information in: <http://gabi-documentation-2020.gabi-software.com/xml-data/processes/db009014-338f-11dd-bd11-0800200c9a66.xml>
- Energy consumption in the biobased fertilizers production process. Energy is consumed in the process in two ways: electricity and diesel. All those consumptions are not known yet and will be determined for each stage of the production process in the implementation phase of the *VALUEWASTE Project* from the exploitation data of the pilot plant. These data will be contrasted

with technical information obtained from bibliographic sources. For determining the environmental burdens related to electricity and natural gas consumption, the following processes included in databases of the GaBi software will be taken.

- *EU-28_Electricity grid mix 1kV-60kV; AC, technology mix; consumption mix, to consumer; 1kV - 60kV.* More information can be found in: <http://gabi-documentation-2020.gabi-software.com/xml-data/processes/0a1b40db-5645-4db8-a887-eb09300b7b74.xml>
 - *EU-28_Diesel mix at filling station; from crude oil and bio components; consumption mix, at filling station; 6.41 wt.% bio components.* More information can be found in: <http://gabi-documentation-2020.gabi-software.com/xml-data/processes/99248ee9-3a59-47e4-b1f1-bb79067249ba.xml>
- Biogas and digestate production. The biogas and digestate production performance with respect to the treated biowaste will be determined in the implementation phase of the *VALUEWASTE Project* from the exploitation data of the pilot plant. From the obtained biogas flow and the remaining part which is available as raw material to the SCP production process will be obtained too. That performance will be contrasted with information obtained from bibliographic sources. Regarding biogas, information about its methane content from the pilot plant exploitation will be also taken.
 - Emissions in anaerobic digestion process. Only the emissions to the air due to the combustion in boiler of the biogas used to maintain the digester temperature will be considered. For calculating these emissions, the methods described in MAPAMA and IPCC will be considered (IPCC, 2006, MAPAMA, 2020).
 - Solid/liquid digestate production. The flows of the solid and liquid fractions of digestate will be determined in the implementation phase of the *VALUEWASTE Project* from the exploitation data of the pilot plant. That information is necessary for making a mass-based impact allocation. All the information coming from the pilot plant will be contrasted with information obtained from bibliographic sources.
 - Compost production. For determining the amount of compost produced from the incoming solid digestate, information from bibliographic sources will be used. Data coming from the characterisation of the digestate solid fraction done in the experimental phase of the project might be used for calculating the produced compost. On the other hand, some composting processes included in databases of the GaBi software might also be used.

- Emissions in composting process. For calculating all these missions, the methods described in MAPAMA and IPCC will be considered (IPCC, 2006, MAPAMA, 2020). On the other hand, some composting processes included in databases of the GaBi software might also be used.
- Emissions due to the application of compost. The compost application to the agricultural soil entails different emissions which are intended to be included in the LCA analysis. First, it is included the direct emissions derived from the activity of the agricultural machinery used for compost application. The amount of diesel consumed regarding the amount of applied compost will be calculated with ratios obtained from bibliographic sources. The combustion gases released by the agricultural machinery will be initially estimated using the methods described in MAPAMA and IPCC (IPCC, 2006; MAPAMA, 2020), besides other bibliographic sources, if necessary.

Another considered air emissions are those which are directly produced when applying the compost to the soil. Initially, emissions of ammonia, methane, and dinitrogen oxide (NH_3 , CH_4 and N_2O) will be considered whenever possible. However, this assumption can be revised after the assessment of diverse bibliographical sources. The emitted quantities will be estimated using the methods described in MAPAMA and IPCC (IPCC, 2006; MAPAMA, 2020), besides other bibliographic sources.

The application of fertilizers to the soil also involves emissions to the freshwater, as it is indicated in several models and studies. For the compost case, and in a first approximation, only the phosphate emission to surface water caused by run-offs will be considered. Averaged ratios from diverse bibliographic references will be used to estimate the amount of emitted phosphate.

The last considered emissions related to compost application are the emission of pollutants to the agricultural soil. For the moment, it is expected to study heavy metals and phosphates. For estimating the emission to agricultural soil of those pollutants, their concentration in the compost produced in the experimental phase of the project will be determined. Then, from the assessment of several bibliographical sources, transfer coefficients for both pollutants, from compost to soil will be defined.

Finally, it is important to note that the transport of the compost from the production to the application site and associated emissions are not included.

- Avoided fertilizers consumption due to the agronomic compost valorisation. The compost includes N and P in its composition, so its application to the agricultural soil can entail savings of mineral fertilizers production. The amount of saved mineral fertilizers will depend on the N and P concentration in these fertilizers, as well as in the compost, and the mineralisation

percentage of N and P from compost. Concentrations of N and P in compost will be calculated using as starting point the composition of the solid fraction of the digestate used to produce it, along with information obtained from bibliographic sources. The percentages of N and P from compost mineralized in soil will be averaged using data coming from diverse references, which will be specified. Calcium ammonium nitrate (27% of N) and triple superphosphate (46% of P₂O₅) will be considered as mineral fertilizers to substitute. For determining the environmental burdens related to fertilizers production, the following processes included in databases of the GaBi software will be taken.

- *EU-28_Calcium ammonium nitrate (CAN, 27% N); neutralising nitric acid with ammonia, including primary production; production mix, at plant; 27 % nitrogen content.* More information can be found in: <http://qabi-documentation-2020.qabi-software.com/xml-data/processes/d069ee25-aebc-4cb5-a3b6-2b976e859d21.xml>
 - *Triple superphosphate (TSP, 46% P₂O₅); rock phosphate acidulation with phosphoric acid, including primary production; production mix, at plant; 46 % phosphate content.* More information can be found in: <http://qabi-documentation-2020.qabi-software.com/xml-data/processes/d069ee25-aebc-4cb5-a3b6-2b976e859d21.xml>
- Struvite production. The performance of the struvite production will be obtained from the exploitation data of the VALUEWASTE pilot plant. Besides the amount of struvite produced with respect to the treated volume of liquid digestate, the following information will be obtained: characterisation of the incoming digestate liquid fraction and the effluent of the process (concentrations of total nitrogen, total phosphorus, N-NH₃ and P-PO₄), characterisation of the obtained struvite sludge (concentrations of dry solids and purity of the obtained struvite). All the experimental information will be contrasted with information obtained from bibliographic sources.
- Emissions in struvite production. Only the emissions to the air due to the combustion of the diesel used will be considered. The pollutants and the emitted amounts will be quantified considering the calculated diesel consumption, and the corresponding emission factors, according to the methods described in MAPAMA and IPCC (IPCC, 2006, MAPAMA, 2020).
- Ammonium sulphate production. The performance of the ammonium sulphate production will be obtained from the exploitation data of the VALUEWASTE pilot plant. Besides the amount of ammonium sulphate produced with respect to the treated volume of water influent, the following information will be obtained: N-NH₃ concentration in water influent and in treated water, dry solids content in the produced sludge of ammonium salts and purity of the (NH₄)₂SO₄

obtained in dry basis. All the experimental information will be contrasted with information obtained from bibliographic sources.

- Emissions in ammonium sulphate production. It will be considered the emissions to the air caused by diesel used and the emissions to freshwater of the pollutants contained in the process effluent. In the first case, the pollutants and the emitted amounts will be quantified considering the calculated diesel consumption, and the corresponding emission factors, according to the methods described in MAPAMA and IPCC (IPCC, 2006, MAPAMA, 2020). In the case of the emissions to freshwater, along the project we will monitor the flow of the water effluent produced and the concentration in the same of some pollutants. With these data the amounts of the pollutants which are emitted to freshwater will be calculated. It is possible that the pH value in the treated water effluent was slightly basic and may stay over the limits for discharging to waterbodies as stated by regulations. In this case samples from that effluent will be taken and will be neutralized in the laboratory of CETENMA, calculating the amount of acid which is necessary for it, so that such treatment can be incorporated into the system which are going to be studied by LCA.

F&F ingredients (dried SCP). Information about material and energy flows and calculation parameters that are going to be used in the development of the Life Cycle Inventory of the process, as well as the considered bibliographic references are described below.

- Activated carbon consumption. The consumption rate will be determined from the analysis of bibliographic sources (technical documents, papers, etc.). For determining the environmental burdens related to activated carbon consumption, the following process included in databases of the GaBi software will be taken.
 - *EU-28_Activated carbon; technology mix; production mix, at plant; porous carbon structure, 35.2 MJ/kg net calorific value*. More information available in: <http://gabi-documentation-2020.gabi-software.com/xml-data/processes/a3944d74-630f-4c44-b1cb-1e72885679ef.xml>
- Activated carbon exhausted treatment. It only will be considered the input of the exhausted carbon and the emissions to the atmosphere. In addition, it will also be taken into account the generation of process energy in the form of electricity and steam. To define the emissions to the air, the energy production process of the coal thermal power plants included in the Spanish emissions inventory (MAPAMA, 2020) will be taken as a reference. For determining the production of heat and electricity, all the treatment processes included in the GaBi software professional database have been analysed. For determining the environmental burdens related

to the avoided production of heat and electricity by using hard coal, the following process included in databases of the GaBi software will be taken.

- *EU-28_Process steam from hard coal 85%; technology mix regarding firing and flue gas cleaning; production mix, at heat plant; MJ, 85% efficiency.* More information in: <http://gabi-documentation-2020.gabi-software.com/xml-data/processes/4100b19a-faf1-4814-b183-e3690db962a8.xml>
 - *EU-28_Electricity from hard coal; AC, mix of direct and CHP, technology mix regarding firing and flue gas cleaning; production mix, at power plant; 1kV – 60kV.* More information in: <http://gabi-documentation-2020.gabi-software.com/xml-data/processes/18b10bc9-2f78-44e5-9a91-2631c6596919.xml>
- Energy consumption. The electricity consumption obtained from different process equipment. The information will be obtained from bibliographic references, such as García Sánchez (2016), Cabrera Delgado (2017) and Romero Lestido (2018), and from the experimental phase of the process. It will be included the consumption of diesel. For determining the environmental burdens related to energy consumption, the following processes included in databases of the GaBi software will be taken.
- *EU-28_Electricity grid mix 1kV-60kV; AC, technology mix; consumption mix, to consumer; 1kV - 60kV.* More information can be found in: <http://gabi-documentation-2020.gabi-software.com/xml-data/processes/0a1b40db-5645-4db8-a887-eb09300b7b74.xml>
 - *EU-28_Diesel mix at filling station; from crude oil and bio components; consumption mix, at filling station; 6.41 wt.% bio components.* More information can be found in: <http://gabi-documentation-2020.gabi-software.com/xml-data/processes/99248ee9-3a59-47e4-b1f1-bb79067249ba.xml>
- Oxygen consumption. The O₂ to be consumed in the SCP production will be defined using foreground data coming from the experimental phase of the project. Gaseous O₂ produced from air by cryogenic separation will be initially considered. Therefore, for determining the environmental burdens related to oxygen consumption, the following process included in databases of the GaBi software.
- *EU-28_Oxygen (gaseous); via cryogenic air separation; production mix, at plant; 1.429 kg/m³, 16.0 g/mol.* More information in: <http://gabi-documentation-2020.gabi-software.com/xml-data/processes/de25dd0e-0072-4e8d-af0d-df6b17c05e1e.xml>

In addition, other possible processes for supplying O₂ will be explored. For example, the production of O₂ from air through an adsorption process and the addition of air will be considered. The process finally selected will depend on the analysis of consumptions and performance, both for its production and its use.

- Chemicals consumption. The consumption of macro and micronutrients, as well as the pH regulators is not known yet. These data will be obtained during the experimental phase of the *VALUEWASTE Project*. For determining the environmental burdens related to the consumption of macronutrients (N and P) and pH regulators, the following processes included in databases of the GaBi software will be taken.
 - *EU-28_Ammonia solution, NH₃ (aq.) (estimation); Haber-Bosch process, from natural gas, diluted solution; production mix, at plant; 35% concentrated.* More information in: <http://gabi-documentation-2020.gabi-software.com/xml-data/processes/cebd938f-51f5-431a-be35-5463c0e850f2.xml>
 - *EU-28_Phosphoric acid (H₃PO₄, 54% P₂O₅); acid digestion of phosphate rock, including primary production; production mix, at plant; 54 %.* More information in: <http://gabi-documentation-2020.gabi-software.com/xml-data/processes/fe9e1855-2fb9-4bc0-874d-a72c3f54de71.xml>
 - *EU-28_Sodium hydroxide (caustic soda) mix (100%); technology mix; production mix, at plant; 1.* More information available in <http://gabi-documentation-2020.gabi-software.com/xml-data/processes/8034f0ff-d0b9-47a8-86e8-ec9772f56871.xml>
 - *EU-28_Sulphuric acid mix (96%); technology mix; consumption mix, to consumer; 96% aqueous solution, M= 98.079 g/mol.* More information can be found in: <http://gabi-documentation-2020.gabi-software.com/xml-data/processes/3e559354-90c2-4851-82e4-36613494940f.xml>

Regarding micronutrients, the type of salts of these compounds and the required quantities are still not known. Similar to the macronutrients case, that information will be obtained along the experimental phase of the *VALUEWASTE Project*.

- SCP production. The biomass production yield information will be obtained from the experimental phase.
- Emissions in SCP production. Currently, only the emissions to the air due to the consumption of the diesel used will be considered. For calculating these emissions, the methods described in MAPAMA and IPCC will be considered (IPCC, 2006, MAPAMA, 2020).

- Treatment of wastewaters produced in SCP production. The volume and composition of wastewater which is produced with respect to the produced biomass are not known yet. It is initially assumed that the wastewater has a low organic load, so it can be directly discharged into the sewer network and finally treated in a municipal wastewater treatment plant (WWTP). However, this assumption must be confirmed and, if required, an additional wastewater treatment process will be considered. Anyway, the final treatment carried out in the WWTP will be included, taking an existing process from GaBi database or one adapted to the produced wastewater. In this case, it will be designed. This will be decided during the experimental phase of the project.

Food & Feed grade protein (insect proteins). Information about material and energy flows and calculation parameters that are going to be used in the development of the Life Cycle Inventory of the process, as well as the considered bibliographic references are described below.

- Tap water consumption. As mentioned, tap water is used in different operations, such as cleaning of equipment. Currently, it is not known the water consumption of the production process with respect to the produced meal or treated biowaste. Those data will be obtained from the experimental phase of the project (foreground data) or from the analysis of bibliographic sources (background data). For determining the environmental burdens related to tap water consumption, the following process included in databases of the GaBi software will be taken.
 - *EU-28_Tap water from surface water; filtration, disinfection, ion removal etc., from surface water; production mix, at plant; 1000 kg/m³, 18 g/mol.* More information in: <http://gabi-documentation-2020.gabi-software.com/xml-data/processes/db009014-338f-11dd-bd11-0800200c9a66.xml>
- Softened water consumption. Its consumption is unknown and will be estimated in the implementation phase of the *VALUEWASTE Project* or from bibliographic sources. For determining the environmental burdens related to softened water consumption, the following process included in databases of the GaBi software will be taken.
 - *EU-28_Process water; ion exchange, from surface water; single route, at plant; 1000 kg/m³, 18 g/mol.* More information available in: <http://gabi-documentation-2020.gabi-software.com/xml-data/processes/db009016-338f-11dd-bd11-0800200c9a66.xml>
- Chemicals consumption. It is forecasted a consumption of chemicals since this is currently unknown. It is hoped that this information can be obtained throughout the experimental phase of the Project.

- Energy consumption in insect meal production. Both electricity and diesel consumption are currently unknown and will be estimated as foreground data from the experimental phase of the project. For determining the environmental burdens related to electricity and natural gas consumption, the following processes included in databases of the GaBi software will be taken.
 - *EU-28_Electricity grid mix 1kV-60kV; AC, technology mix; consumption mix, to consumer; 1kV - 60kV.* More information in: <http://gabi-documentation-2020.gabi-software.com/xml-data/processes/0a1b40db-5645-4db8-a887-eb09300b7b74.xml>
 - *EU-28_Diesel mix at filling station; from crude oil and bio components; consumption mix, at filling station; 6.41 wt.% bio components.* More information can be found in: <http://gabi-documentation-2020.gabi-software.com/xml-data/processes/99248ee9-3a59-47e4-b1f1-bb79067249ba.xml>
- Other consumptions in insect protein production. Some insumes will be considered to be included in the future if they have significative consumptions. This will be confirmed or not when experimental data is available.
- Biowaste / solid digestate consumption and Insect meal / compost production. It is not currently known the insect meal / compost production yield with respect to both, consumed biowaste and consumed solid digestate. These data will be obtained during the experimental phase of the project, as long as the results are representative of an industrial scale process.
- Emissions in insect meal production. The released pollutants and its quantities will be measured or estimated in the experimental phase of the project. Diesel will be used. For calculating these emissions, the methods described by MAPAMA and IPCC will be considered (IPCC, 2006, MAPAMA, 2020). Other type of emission to the atmosphere could be expected in this stage, being included in the analysis if required and can be estimated.
- Emissions due to the application of compost. The same assumptions and calculation procedures defined above for the application of the compost produced from the solid fraction of the digestate are applied in this point.
- Avoided fertilizers consumption due to the agronomic compost valorisation. The same assumptions and calculation procedures defined above for the avoided production of mineral fertilizers due the application of the compost produced from the solid fraction of the digestate are applied in this point. The only difference is that, in this case, the amount of N and P in the compost produced by BSF can be determined from the compost characterisation performed during the experimental phase of the project. In the case of the compost produced by a typical

aerobic process, the N and P concentrations will be calculated, using as a starting point the composition of the solid fraction of the digestate used to produce it, along with information obtained from bibliographic sources.

- Treatment of wastewaters produced in insect meal production. Wastewater streams are produced in different steps of the production process. It will be supposed that these streams have a low enough organic load to be directly discharge into the sewer, being treated afterwards in a municipal WWTP. Currently, the volume of wastewater produced and composition is unknown. Data will be obtained from the experimental works done in the project. If required, an additional wastewater treatment process for adapting the wastewater discharge to the legal requirements will be considered. Anyway, the final treatment carried out in the WWTP will be included, taking an existing process from GaBi database or one adapted to the produced wastewater. In this case, it will be designed. This will be decided during the experimental phase of the project.

It is important to bear in mind that for the insect meal case, two production system will be studied. This will entail the development of two different inventories and, consequently, obtaining two different impacts for the same product, depending on the considered production system. The difference depends on the used raw material: biowaste or the solid fraction obtained when dewatering the digestate produced by anaerobic digestion.

Biowaste case. The input flow will not have any environmental burden from previous stages (e.g., the production in households or its collection and transport) because these stages are not considered since they are similar in all studied cases. **Solid digestate.** This is used as a substrate, having environmental burdens due to the consumptions and emissions of the previous treatment stages. All the environmental impact of the anaerobic digestion process will be divided by three since three products will be obtained in the process (biogas, and the solid and liquid fractions of the digestate). Thus, the environmental burden of the solid fraction used as a raw material will be included in the environmental impact of the insect meal production. Once the inventories of these two cases have been obtained, the inventory of an assumption in which the feed is a mixture of both substrates would be calculated directly by averaging each flow according to the participation factors of each component in the mixture (mass allocation).

When all the inputs and outputs are defined, quantified and standardized regarding the functional unit, the corresponding inventories will be finished and used in the impact assessment phase.

4.5.3. Life Cycle Impact Assessment

The life cycle impact assessment (LCIA) aims at evaluating the significance of potential environmental impacts based on the LCI flow results. In order to evaluate the environmental impacts, different methodologies like CML 2, ReCiPe, EIDP, Eco-indicator or TRACI, are available. The LCA modelling will be performed using the GaBi software, which contains diverse methodologies like those previously mentioned. The available methodologies for impact assessment include a number of specific impact categories, such as Global Warming Potential at 100 years (GWP100), acidification potential (AP), eutrophication potential (EP) and ozone depletion potential (ODP). Thus, the selection of the appropriate methodologies is based on the objectives of the LCA, as well as the particularities of the studied systems.

4.5.4. Interpretation of Results

The interpretation of the results allows, among other things, identifying the hotspots in the studied systems as well as recommending options to reduce the environmental burdens. This allows determining which processes or flows are more relevant for every impact category.

In this way, a contribution analysis will be performed to interpret the impact assessment results. This analysis will show the influence of each process and/or flow in the environmental impact for all the studied systems. Each system will be analysed by a contribution analysis, whose classification can be observed in Table 2 (Haya Leiva, 2016). According to specialist sources, those processes with a negligible impact can be rejected only if the sum of all of them is not higher than 5% of the total impact. Afterwards, a new LCA without these processes will be performed since results of contribution analysis may provide opportunities for redesign, prevention strategies, etc. BASELINE and VALUEWASTE systems will be compared to observe what processes provide differences in the considered impact categories.

In addition to contribution analysis, there are other interpretation analyses which might be considered during the LCA process. These might be carried out as a function of the results obtained during the impact evaluation.

Table 2 – Classification of a process influence as a function of its contribution

Classification	Contribution	Influence
A	Higher than 50%	Significant
B	50% - 25%	Relevant
C	25% - 10%	Important
D	10% - 2.5%	Minor
E	Lower than 2.5%	Negligible

4.6. Upcoming tasks

The activities that have been carried out so far are the definition of all the systems which are going to be assessed, both in BASELINE case and *VALUEWASTE* system, the objective and scope of the E-LCA study to develop, and the methods which are going to be followed for the LCA assessment. Regarding the definition of the Inventory for all the considered systems, the flows which will conform those inventories, and how these flows are going to be quantified, have been identified.

The following step is to define the mentioned inventories for allowing the development of the life cycle impact assessment for every considered product. For defining the inventories of the systems that integrate the *VALUEWASTE* solution, it is necessary to collect information coming from the exploitation of the experimental facilities of the project. In the case of the BASELINE, that information comes from technical bibliographic sources and from the processes available in the databases of the software to use. Therefore, the inventories of the BASELINE can be already calculated, and for this reason this will be the first task to carry out. Afterwards, with the pilot plant operating, it will probably be possible to obtain all the needed information for defining the inventories of the *VALUEWASTE* system. It is important to note that only the information coming from the experimental phase of the project will be used, that being representative of an industrially implemented process.

Once the inventories of all the production processes are defined, the life cycle impact assessment (LCIA) will be carried out for all of them. For that purpose, several methods to evaluate the environmental impacts will be considered, with the most suitable one being selected. The study will be performed using GaBi software and will select a method included in the mentioned software to evaluate the selected impact categories.

Once the LCIA is done, a subsequent contribution analysis will allow to discard those processes with a negligible influence in the impact of the system where they are. Along with that, the LCA will allow to identify hotspots in each of the production processes studied. Then, the comparative analysis between the environmental impacts of the considered products, depending on if they are obtained with the BASELINE production processes or with *VALUEWASTE*' ones, will be carried out. Afterwards, and as a function of both the LCA objective and the obtained results, the interpretation of results procedures will be defined and carried out.

5. Conclusions

The LCA methodology will be applied to assess the *VALUEWASTE* solution from social and environmental perspectives within the WP6 - Future large-scale projects. Hence, throughout the present deliverable, both S-LCA and E-LCA methodologies have been shown beside their goal and scope.

S-LCA → The S-LCA will be carried out to assess and identify the hotspots (social impacts) of the stakeholders involved in the *VALUEWASTE* solution. In this way, all partners will be included in this study. Therefore, the Consortium will be considered as an organization itself.

To achieve this goal, another methodology has to be applied to assess the S-LCA which has been developed throughout the present report. This methodology is based on the UNEP/SETAC guideline and diverse studies published. Therefore, the basis to carry out a S-LCA within the framework of *VALUEWASTE* has been established.

The following step is to define those stakeholders, subcategories and social indicators to be assessed. This will allow to prepare the information source: the survey to be used.

E-LCA → In the case of the E-LCA, a baseline system has been proposed to be compared to *VALUEWASTE* solution. This fact will allow assessing the environmental improvement of *VALUEWASTE* solution. The first step to address in this study is to identify all flows that will comprise the inventories and how they are going to be quantified. This first step has been widely developed in the present deliverable.

The following step is to get the required information to define the inventories. In the case of *VALUEWASTE*, this information will be obtained from the experimental facilities, as well as from technical bibliography and processes included in the databases of GaBi software. In the case of the baseline, the information will be obtained from technical bibliography and processes included in the databases of GaBi software.

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